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INDIAN DISASTER MANAGEMENT: A CASE STUDY OF UTTARAKHAND STATE

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Abstract: -

The world has been facing problem due to Natural Disaster from the past time. Every year many countries in the world are affected by this natural disaster. India is also among those affected areas of world, where every year damages and loss of huge amount of capital and life of people occur, due to this natural disaster. In India different types of natural disaster (i.e. Flood, Earthquake, Tsunami, and Drought etc.) occur every year. To deal this type of natural disaster, India passed Disaster Management Act 2005 and later on National Disaster Management Authority (NDM) and State Disaster Management Authorities (SDMAs). In this paper we study about role of Disaster Management in Natural Disaster and weakness of Indian Disaster Management. And also we take the case study of Uttarakhand state, where heavy floods affected different area of this state and caused huge loss of man and capital. In this case study, we describe what type of actions is taken by Indian government and various forces. We also try to describe the mismanagement of state disaster authority at past and present time.

Keywords: - Disaster Management, Uttarakhand, Hydel Power Plant, Government, CAG

1. Introduction: -

1.1. Disaster Management-

Natural Disaster has affected many area of India from past time. In India many people had died and huge amount of capital loss had occurred in past times. In order to reduce deaths and capital losses Indian Government passed Disaster Management Act 2005. According to this Act, “Disaster means a catastrophe, mishap, calamity or grave occurrence in any area, arising from natural or manmade causes, or by accident or negligence which results in substantial loss of life or human suffering or damage to, and destruction of, property, or damage to, or degradation of, environment, and is of such a nature or magnitude as to be beyond the coping capacity of the community of the affected area”. Disaster Management means a continuous and integrated process of planning, organizing, coordinating and implementing measures which are necessary or expedient for :-

1. Prevention of danger or threat of any disaster.
2. Mitigation or reduction of risk of any disaster or its severity or consequences.

3. Capacity-building.
4. Preparedness to deal with any disaster.
5. Prompt response to any threatening disaster situation or disaster.
6. Assessing the severity or magnitude of effects of any disaster.
7. Evacuation, Rescue and Relief.
8. Rehabilitation and Reconstruction.

1.2. National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA): -

The Disaster Management Act mandates the NDMA to lay down policies and guidelines for the statutory authorities to draw their plans. In essence, the NDMA will concentrate on prevention, mitigation, preparedness, rehabilitation and reconstruction and also formulate appropriate policies and guidelines for effective and synergized national disaster response and relief. It will coordinate the enforcement and implementation of policies and plans.

1.3. State Disaster Management Authority (SDMA)/ State Executive Committee (SEC): -

The Disaster Management Act 2005 provides that there shall be a DM plan for every state. It outlines the broad coverage of the plan as well as the requirements of consultation in the preparation of the state plans. It also provides for annual review and updating of the state plan, and enjoins upon the state governments to make provisions for financing the activities to be carried out under the state plans. It provides for the departments of the state governments to draw up their own plans in accordance with the state plan. The state plans shall be prepared by the SEC in conformity with the guidelines to be issued on related matters by the SDMA having regard to the guidelines laid down in this regard by the NDMA, and after such consultation with local and district authorities and the people’s representatives as the SEC may deem fit. The state plan prepared by SEC shall be approved by the SDMA.

1.4. National Disaster Response Force (NDRF): -

The National Disaster Response Force has been constituted for the purpose of specialist response to a threatening disaster situation or disaster. It has 10 Bns at Guwahati, Kolkata, Mundali, Arakkonam, Pune, Gandhinagar, Bhatinda and Greater Noida, Patna and Vijayawada. Of these, four Bns are meant for tackling Nuclear, Biological and Chemical (NBC) disasters also. In addition to search & rescue operations, the NDRF has been deployed on the sites of train accidents, collapsed structures, capsized boats, bus accidents, landslides, cloudburst and in the cases of drowning etc. besides duties to assist the civil authorities in various States.

Figure No. 1.1, National structure for disaster management

2. Literature Survey: -

Building culture of prevention is not easy. While the cost of prevention had to be paid in the present, its benefits lie in the distant future. Moreover, the benefits are not tangible; they are disasters that did not happen (Kofi Annan, UN Secretary General, 1999).

The United Nations' declaration of 1990-2000 as the International Decade for Natural Disaster Reduction (IDNDR) was not only instrumental in bringing into sharp focus the devastations caused by natural disasters, but it also introduced a paradigm shift from focusing on post-disaster relief and reconstruction to adopting a pre-disaster pro-active approach. In May 1994, a mid-term review of the UN declaration held at Yokohama, which was attended by Governments, NGOs, scientists and representatives of business, trade and industry [1].

The Yokohama message emanating from the international decade for natural disaster reduction in May, 1994 underlined the need for an emphatic shift in the strategy for disaster mitigation. It was inter alia stressed that disaster prevention, mitigation, preparedness and relief are four elements which contribute to and gain, from the implementation of the sustainable development policies. These elements along with environmental protection and sustainable development, are closely inter related. A Disaster Risk Management Programmed has been taken up with the assistance from UNDP, USAID and European Union in 169 most hazard prone districts in 17 States including all the 8 North Eastern State. The implementation of the project commenced from October, 2002 and is expected to be concluded by December, 2007 [2].

The study shows that between 1950 and 2010, there were 19,370 great natural disasters globally costing the world \$2.1trillion with over 2,300,000 fatalities. It is recommended that for sustainable development, disaster prevention and risk management should be features that every country must take seriously. While it is difficult to prevent the occurrence of some of the natural disasters like earthquakes, volcanoes and windstorms, adequate risk management policies and measures should always be put in place especially countries within the pacific ring of fire of the world that is mostly affected by these disasters. Global disasters management agencies and organizations should have prompt rescue measures while the rich nations should assist the affected poor nations irrespective of bilateral relationships prior to the disaster [03].

International humanitarian agencies have developed an impressive operational capacity in disaster response and international development agencies are leading the way in advocating for disaster risk reduction. Regional organizations also add value in cases where disasters have regional consequences – whether through warning systems for tsunamis or sharing seismic data or monitoring volcanic activity [04].

There has been immense change in both human and environmental conditions over the past 30 years. In an unprecedented period of population increase, the environment has been heavily drawn upon to meet a multiplicity of human needs. In many areas, the state of the environment is much more fragile and degraded than it was in 1972. Overall, policy measures have not been adequate to counteract the pressures imposed by increasing poverty and uncontrolled consumption [05].

The natural disasters can be reduced by setting up advanced warning systems, which forecast the impending natural disasters timely. The consequences of the natural disasters also can be reduced through an effective disaster management. In addition to this, natural and man- made disasters can also be prevented or reduced through public involvement in disaster management policies, books, video, conducting workshop and training programmed, community participation, capacity building, mock drills etc [06].

India in the recent years has made significant development in the area of disaster management. A new culture of preparedness, quick response, strategic thinking and prevention is being ushered. The

administrative framework is being streamlined to deal with the various disasters. Effort are also being made to make disaster management a community movement wherein there is greater participation of the people. However, a lot more need to be done to make disaster management a mass movement in near future [07].

The pressure on the earth's resources caused by increased population has resulted in increased vulnerability of human and their infrastructure to the natural hazards, which have always existed. Space technology can help the disaster mitigation process through better future scenario predictions; detection of disaster prone areas; location of protection measures and safe alternate routes etc [08].

Integrated natural disaster risk management is relatively an advanced approach and system for disaster prevention, mitigation and management, and is being paid more attention by disaster managers and researchers in the world [09].

However, planning and training are not enough: one must plan for the right things. Valuable lessons can be learned from formal disaster research studies [10].

Such an approach would provide the space and opportunity for both women and men to take part in the risk management process more constructively, improve their risk management skills, expand their potential, so that they will in turn, change from 'helpless victims' to a 'useful resource' [11].

Lessons from India can have wider applications as many other countries share the common challenge of deciding how to best link the two parallel tracks for tackling climate adaptation and disaster management [12].

Political determination, effective and efficient policy implementation and the participation of the public are of prime importance in achieving these goals [13]. Devices and user interfaces must be tailored to hostile environments and to users who are often not computer literate. Application and information flow designers must consider fast-changing working environments, and resource management is a challenge given the chaotic nature of disasters [14].

Focus on mitigation to reduce greenhouse gas emissions alone, however, is not enough. There has to be greater focus on building community resilience and minimizing vulnerability through adaptation measures for climate change impacts as well – including those from changing patterns of natural hazard occurrence and intensity. Policies on climate change of disaster management and land use planning need to be linked together more strongly by local councils to deal with both mitigation and adaptation measures [15].

3. Disaster Scenario in India and World:-

India accounts for the one fifth of the deaths caused due to flooding across the world. 24 out of the 35 states and Union Territories are vulnerable to these disasters. Annually, an average of about 18.6 million hectare of land area and 3.7 million hectare crop area are affected by flooding. More than 190 power and mining projects are running in 14 rivers valleys in Uttarakhand. Union Ministry of environment and forests issued a notification, declaring the entire watershed area around the 135 Km stretch between Gaumukh and Uttarakhshi, along the Bhagirathi river, as an eco-sensitive zone under the environment Protection Act 1986. This bans all construction activity in the area. Total direct losses due to natural disasters in 40 low and middle income countries amount to \$305 billion over the last 30 years. Direct disaster losses are at least 50% higher than internationally reported figures. Globalized supply chains create new vulnerabilities: Toyota lost \$1.2 billion in revenue from the 2011 Japan earthquake; India worst affected with reductions in production by 70%. SEZs are considered high risk zones. The number of export oriented SEZs has expanded from 176 zones in 47 countries in 1986 to 3,500 zones in 130 countries in 2006. 45 aircraft and helicopters as well as over 10,000 troops working to rescue stranded people, provide relief material and restore communication Army has also deployed over 100 special forces troops in Kedarnath and Sonprayag area, which is cut off

IAF choppers, which have flown over 150 sorties so far, have airdropped 20,000kg of food and relief material. Casualties in the affected areas may run into thousands with about 90 "dharamashalas" (rest houses for pilgrims) swept away in the flash floods over 240 mm of rain lashed the high Himalayan region; leading to flash floods, landslides, blocked roads and stranded people.

Table No. 3.1, Total number of people reported killed and affected by disasters in World and its Continents

Total number of people reported killed and affected by disasters in World and its Continents						
Region	Total No. of people killed (1992-2001)	Total No. of people affected(1992-2001)	Total No. of people killed(2002-2011)	Total No. of people affected(2002-2011)	Total No. of people killed(2011)	Total No. of people affected(2011)
Africa	34138	256306685	43563	292258082	3464	19091870
Americas	78748	60176559	257325	88219302	3340	13457402
Asia	733557	1965633824	786159	2294859811	28751	176453329
Europe	36587	43484114	145770	7335183	1557	78890
Oceania	3397	38798923	1807	1656545	221	484486
World	886427	2364400105	1234624	2684328923	37333	209565977

Table No. 3.2, India's Major Disasters

India's Major Disasters			
Sr. No.	Name of Event	Year	State & Area
1.	Drought	1972	Large part of the country
2.	Cyclone	1977	Andhra Pradesh
3.	Drought	1987	15 States
4.	Earthquake	1991	Uttarkashi (Uttaranchal)
5.	Latur Earthquake	1993	Latur, Marathwada region of Maharashtra
6.	Floods	1993	Punjab
7.	Orissa Super Cyclone	1999	Orissa
8.	Gujarat Earthquake	2001	Rapar, Bhuj, Bhachau, Anjar, Ahmedabad and Surat in Gujarat State
9.	Tsunami	2004	Coastline of Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Andhra Pradesh, Pondicherry and Andaman and Nicobar Islands of India
10.	Fire Tragedy	2004	Kumbakonam (Tamilnadu)
11.	Maharashtra Floods	2005	Maharashtra State
12.	Kashmir Earthquake	2005	Mostly Pakistan, Partially Kashmir
13.	Kosi Floods	2008	North Bihar
14.	Cyclone Nisha	2008	Tamil Nadu
15.	Drought	2009	252 districts in 10 states
16.	Leh Cloudburst	2010	Leh, Ladakh in Jammu & Kashmir
17.	Sikkim Earthquake	2011	North-eastern India with epicenter near Nepal Border and Sikkim
18.	Cyclone	2011	Thane

Figure No 3.1, Natural Disaster Occurrence Reported during 1980-2010 in India

Figure No. 3.2, Disasters distributions according to No. of Death (Left) and Economic Loss (US \$ bn) (Right) in India.

Figure No 3.3, Percentage Distributions of Reported Disaster in India (Left) and Average Annual Economic Loss (USD million) of India (Right)

Source: UNISDR (2010)

Table No. 3.3, Maximum Damage Due to Flood in India

Maximum Damage Due to Flood in India	
Affected Area(Mha)	17.50
Population Affected (Millions)	70.45
Damage to Crops (RsCrores)	4246.62
Damage to houses (RsCrores)	1307.89
Damage to Public Utilities (RsCrores)	5604.46
Cattle Lost ('000)	618
Human Life Lost (No.)	11316
Total Damages to Crops Houses and Public Utilities (RsCrores)	8864.54

Source: CWC (2010)

Figure No. 3.4. Different types of Loss by disaster in 2002 to 2011. Source: MHA

Table No. 3.4, Natural Disasters in India from 1980 – 2010

Natural Disasters in India from 1980 – 2010	
No of events	431
No of people killed	143,039
Average killed per year	4,614
No of people affected	1,521,726,127
Average affected per year	49,087,940
Economic Damage (US\$ X 1,000)	48,063,830
Economic Damage per year (US\$ X 1,000)	1,550,446

Source: Prevention web

4. Case Study: -

In this paper we have chosen the case study of Uttarakhand State in India, Where heavy flood occurs in different places of this state. The details of Uttarakhand state is described below:-

4.1. Location -

Uttarakhand is located between 28° 43' – 31° 27' N latitudes and 77° 34' – 81° 02' E longitudes. The river Tons separates the state from Himachal Pradesh in the north-west, whereas the river Kali separates it from Nepal in the east. The greater Himalaya is the northern boundary of the state and is also the international border with China (Tibet). Foot-hills in the south are bound by Uttar Pradesh. The region, being situated centrally in the long sweep of the Himalaya, forms a transitional zone between the per-humid eastern and the dry to sub-humid western Himalaya. It is often referred to as the "Land of the Gods" due to the many holy Hindu temples and pilgrim centers found throughout the state.

4.2. Population-

The total population of Uttarakhand state as per details from Census 2011, Uttarakhand has population of 1.01 Crores, an increase from figure of 84.89 Lakh in 2001 census. Total population of Uttarakhand as per 2011 census is 10,086,292 of which male and female are 5,137,773 and 4,948,519 respectively. In 2001, total population was 8,489,349 in which males were 4,325,924 while females were 4,163,425. The total population growth in this decade was 18.81 percent while in previous decade it was 19.20 percent. The population of Uttarakhand forms 0.83 percent of India in 2011. In 2001, the figure was 0.83 percent.

4.3. Area -

Total area of Uttarakhand is 53,483 sq. km. Density of Uttarakhand is 189 per sq km which is lower than national average 382 per sq km. In 2001, density of Uttarakhand was 159 per sq km, while nation average in 2001 was 324 per sq km.

4.4. Background of Uttarakhand Disaster: -

Uttarakhand is a disaster prone state. Landslides, forest fires, cloudbursts and flashfloods are seasonal in nature and these strikes at a certain period of the year with high frequency. Earthquakes are the most devastating in the mountains and are unpredictable. So far, in the recent years (1990 onwards) Uttarakhand has experienced two major earthquakes (magnitude > 6) in Uttarkashi (1991) and Chamoli (1999) and a series of landslides/cloud burst such as Malpa (1998), Okhimath (1998), Fata (2001), Gona (2001), KhetGaon (2002), Budhakedar (2002), Bhatwari(2002), Uttarkashi (2003), Amparav (2004), Lambagar (2004), Govindghat(2005), Agastyamuni(2005) and Ramolsari(2005) [7]. In fact Rudraprayag has faced monsoon related major disasters SEVEN times in last 34 years, including in 1979, 1986, 1998, 2001, 2005, 2006 and 2012, each involving death and destruction. Geological Survey of [India](#) had identified 101 of the 233 Uttarakhand villages affected by the disaster of of 2008 as vulnerable. The state potentially lost an interest of Rs 9.96 crores between 2007 and 2011 because it did not properly invest its funds.

Table No. 4.1, Loss of life due to natural calamities during 2007-08 to 2011-12

Loss of life due to natural calamities during 2007-08 to 2011-12	
Type of Disaster	No. of Life Lost
Heavy Rains	186
Landslides	175
Cloud burst/Earthquake	118
Fire Accidents	26
Avalanche	13
Miscellaneous	135
Total	653

Source: Department of Disaster Management, Uttarakhand

4.5. Uttarakhand Disaster – 2012: -

1. In fact in August 2012, Uttarkashi district saw similar tragedy that left 29 dead, many more missing and collapse of houses like card board boxes.
2. Similarly in Sept 2012, Okhimath in Rudraprayag district (one of the epicenters of current tragedy) saw monsoon induced landslides killing 69 people among other damages.

Table No. 4.2, Details of Uttarakhand State Damage Due to Cyclonic Storm/ Floods/Landslides/ Cloudburst etc. during 2012-13

Details of Uttarakhand State Damage Due to Cyclonic Storm/ Floods/Landslides/ Cloudburst etc. during 2012-13	
No. of human lives lost	201
No. of cattle heads lost	705
No. of houses damaged	5569
Cropped area affected (lakh hectares)	0.3854

4.6. Details of Uttarakhand Disaster – 2013: -

All four Pilgrimage centers (Gangotri, Yamunotri, Kedarnath and Badrinath) and the fifth one of Hemkunt Sahib have faced some serious floods this season. In addition, areas of Pithoragarh (Goriganga basin) and Himachal Pradesh (Kinnaur district, mainly Kashang area, a tributary of Sutlej) basin also faced floods during the same period. The rainfall event that leads to these floods started on June 15 and went on till June 16-17. It seems strange to see such vast area facing simultaneous high intensity rainfall. Kedarnath shrine saw two massive flood events, on 16 and 17 June 2013. The flood witnessed at the shrine (located at 3584 m above msl) originated from catchment that includes two mountain peaks: Kedarnath and Kedarnath Dome (6831 m elevation). Following torrential rains possibly triggered by cloude burst, huge boulders broke away from Kedar Dome and ruptured the downstream charbari lake reservoir, about 6 km upstream from the temple along the Mandakini river.

Another instance of GLOF in this Uttarakhand flood disaster could have happened at Hemkunt Sahib Pilgrim centre (elevation 4632 m), the level of water in the lake surrounding the shrine suddenly “increased as glacier from the uphill came down.”

However, from all accounts, the massive rainfall and cloud burst events were happening at multiple places, including in Bhagirathi basin, Assiganga basin, Mandakini Basin, Badrinath region, other places in Alaknanda region, among others. The massive amount of muck deposited on the Alaknanda riverbed by the under construction 330 MW GVK Srinagar Alaknanda Hydropower Project (the project has had no credible environmental impact assessment) accentuated the flood disaster in the downstream area. The sudden release of water from the dam along with the illegally dumped muck in the river bed lead to disaster in downstream Srinagar town. In Rudraprayag (this is likely to be one of the Mandakini hydropower projects, either PhataByuang or SingoliBhatwari), the muck of the dam was deposited along the river which has diverted the course of water. A large number of hydropower projects are likely to have suffered damage due to the flood disaster in Uttarakhand and Himachal Pradesh. Some of the projects that have suffered damage include:

1. 400 MW Vishnuprayag HEP of JP Associates has suffered serious, but as yet unassisted damage.
2. 76 MW PhataByung HEP of Lanco in Mandakini Valley in Uttarakhand.
3. 99 MW SingoliBhatwari HEP of L&T in Mandakini Valley in Uttarakhand.
4. Kali Ganga I, Kali Ganga II and Madhyamaheshwar HEP, all in Mandakini Valley, all of UJVNL, all hit by mudslides.
5. Assiganga I-IV projects on Assigangariver in Bhagirathi basin in Uttarakhand.
6. Small HEP in Goriganga basin in Pithoragarh.
7. 65 MW Kashang HEP in Sutlej basin in Himachal Pradesh.
8. 280 Dhauliganga Project of NHPC in Pithoragarh district of Uttarakhand.

4.7. Causes of Disaster in uttarakhand state: -

In a state like Uttarakhand, which is prone to disasters like cloud bursts, flash floods, landslides, the indiscriminate building of hundreds of hydropower projects in this state, each project entailing dam, tunnels that need to be blasted through, the roads, townships and deforestation, the disaster and damage potential goes up multi fold, particularly when there are no credible environment of social impact assessments at project or basin level, nor any carrying capacity study, nor any credible compliance mechanisms. Even the wrong operation of projects can add to the disaster potential. The main cause of Uttarakhand Disaster was man itself and basically those persons who are top most position in Indian Government. In our system man thinks about only benefits itself. Man thinks that there is no need to care about that Disaster and loss of man when we look our profits or benefits. The main causes of this disaster in Uttarakhand state is described below.

1. Weather warning about the heavy rains was not given wide publicity beforehand by the Government agencies and the Indian Meteorological Department.
2. We do not have credible environmental-impact assessment of infrastructure projects on these highly ecologically sensitive areas. Neither is there any credible mechanism to assure compliance with environmental regulations. These are places where there is a heavy tourist influx. The collapse of buildings like a set of playing cards shows these were encroachments on the riverbed and floodplains.
3. Constructions of illegal buildings and mining, and throwing all norms into the air. And at time of destruction, most contractors habitually thro this debris in river resulting in reduced water carrying capacity of rivers.
4. Rapid Deforestation and inaction towards unchecked construction work, hydropower projects, and mining projects. Due to deforestation, soil erosion and leading to massive landslides.
5. Several Rivers are being diverted through tunnels and blasts carried out for these in uncontrolled manners. Tunnels are being built to divert them rivers for hydel projects and constant blasting of the river banks has affected the flow of water has been eroded as a consequences.
6. The Hydel power projects have been undertaken without assessing their impact on the environment.
7. Even gazette notification of 135 kms of Bhagirathi as an Eco sensitive Zone came in pretty late from the MoEF and is being opposed by the Uttarakhand Government.

Beside these causes the CAG report point out that, "Nor has it made any 'rules, regulations, policies or guidelines', a preliminary step for the authority to have any functional meaning. The state authorities were virtually non-functional. And notify the reasons of this disaster and mismanagement of Indian Government and State Government, which described below.

1. State Government management authority, which was formed in October 2007 has neither ever met till date, nor has it made any rules and guidelines for its functioning. The state disaster management plan was under preparation and actionable programmed were not prepared for various disasters.
2. State did not even have the mandatory disaster management plan prescribed by the Disaster Management Act of 2005. The actionable programmed for various disasters were still under preparation when disaster struck though these should have been well in place given that Uttarakhand has a history of being hit by natural disasters.
3. The state has not even mapped the frequency and intensity various types of disasters it has suffered. Besides, there was no plan prepared for early warning of disasters and the communication system was inadequate. This has often resulted in delayed information to vulnerable people.
4. The communication system was inadequate.

5. The central government released no funds for the states disaster management in 2011-12 because there was no accounting of previous funds.
6. The state disaster management authority did not even have basic personnel in place.
7. Government has failure to rehabilitate 80 villages which had been affected by various disasters in the past.
8. At the district level 44% posts in the District Emergency Operations Cells were laying vacant, thus paralyzing emergency response efforts.
9. There were no master trainers to train staff at the district, block and village level for prevention and mitigation of disasters. No medical personnel were trained in hospital preparedness.
10. An environment assessment of the Bhagirathi and Alaknanda, the erosion in river may causes floods in future.
11. The report had also cautioned both the Central and State Government that mushrooming hydel projects on the two rivers causing damages to the two hills besides increasing the possibility of flash floods.

A United Nations (UN) report has warned India that it is at greater risk by opting for public private partnership (PPP) mode of investment for raising its public infrastructure where the government has less control over its executing private partners and the latter has little interest in long term safety of the projects. A UN study, the Global Assessment Report (GAR) on disaster risk reduction, released earlier this month for Asia Pacific has warned India of its huge infrastructure assets exposed to disaster risk, something like what we have experienced post release of the report in Uttarakhand where flash floods have washed away properties worth thousands of crores while thousands have perished.

The 2013 GAR study on disaster risk reduction is the third biennial report coordinated by the UN's Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNISDR) and has analyzed many of the country's largest infrastructure projects for their risk exposure to natural and man-made calamities. The GAR warns India -- which has projected nearly \$1 trillion worth of investments for infrastructure development in the 12th Five Year Plan - of greater economic losses from unsafe public property facing disaster risk. The report puts the estimated exposure of economic assets in Mumbai alone to increase from \$46 billion in 2005 to \$1,598 billion in 2070. Other Indian cities where large PPP assets are planned face similar risk. Owing to economic and urban growth, natural and artificial subsidence, sea level rise and climate change, this exposure is likely to increase dramatically, particularly in low and middle income countries.

4.8. Rescue Operation during Uttarakhand Disaster - 2013: -

Uttarakhand is prone to natural disasters like earthquake, cloud-burst and flood, rock slope failures, including landslides, and forest fires. There are three stages of disaster management to tackle the situation. First stage comprise of mapping, capacity building, documentation and creation of data base along with warning systems. The second phase consists of search & rescue, disposal, relief etc and the last phase, referred to as post disaster management, includes loss arrangement, relief provision, rehabilitation etc. Army, ITBP and National Disaster Response Force have launched one of the biggest human rescue operations. In conditions made desperately difficult as result of roads being washed away, around 10,000 soldiers and dozens of helicopters were spearheading efforts to reach people that had been cut off since monsoon rains hit. According to India's home ministry a total of 33,100 people had been rescued so far but that at least 50,400 are still stranded. India's NDTV television channel said a further 14,000 people remain unaccounted for and that officials and rescue workers are concerned the death toll in the Himalaya an state of Uttarakhand could leap.

4.9. Some of the immediate priority actions that need to be taken to reduce the impact of such disasters in the state: -

1. Put in place a credible warning and forecasting mechanism.
2. Review of ongoing development works and scrap those that are going to increase the disaster and damage potential.
3. Put in place well defined Disaster Management Plan, with standard operating procedures that would kick in when there is either warning of incidence of disaster.
4. Credible cumulative impact assessment, including carrying capacity study for each river basin, for all existing and under construction projects, stop all new projects till then, including those where not more than 20% money is spent, till this is done.
5. Assess buildings and hotels in the river bed and phase them out before next monsoon, similarly assess other risky structures.

5. Result and Discussion: -

We need an action plan on how the relief material would be received, where it would be stored and how it would be distributed. The welfare (boarding and lodging) of the rescue team personnel should also be taken care off. There should be a plan in place for utilization of funds on emergency measures and long time mitigation measures. If a post disaster management plan is ready, active and properly executed, lots of life can be saved and suffering of effected population can be reduced to some extent.

On long term basis, Geographic Information System (GIS) can be a useful tool for storage, retrieval and manipulation of relevant spatial and non spatial data, maps and information and can also be developed as a decision making system for disaster management. For immediate relief and action an expert committee can be helpful in developing a suitable strategy for post disaster management.

Increasingly, in India, PPPs are emerging preferred mode of investment for publicly managed construction. These partnerships do not necessarily lead to improved disaster risk assessment and management, and may underplay disaster risks or lead to their transfer as shared costs to the public sector or to city residents. Uttarakhand is prone to such events; manmade climate change is going to increase the frequency of such events.

6. Conclusions:-

This type destruction can be prevented to great extent if the laws formulated to save the environment are implemented duly. Government of India has setup many bodies to control floods and for rescue operations, it would be best that strictest measures are taken to prevent such disaster in future, as prevention is better than cure. Keeping in mind all these factors, there is an urgent need to immediately take certain measures. Few of them are

1. top the ongoing hydel projects in Uttarakhand
2. Address pending issues raised by communities and groups
3. undertake transparent and true carrying capacity study of the region
4. scrap 24 projects mentioned by WII and more,
5. consider geological impacts,
6. monitor commissioned projects closely for compliance,
7. decommission commissioned projects which flout environmental norms or have a severe downstream impact,
8. Manage 135 kms Eco-sensitive zone on bhagirathi, and also have a similar one for Alaknanda and near all river origins in Uttarakhand.

They (India Meteorological Department) need to develop a more precise observational and forecasting capability. IMD followed a standard format of weather forecast and used certain terminologies like rainfall, heavy rainfall, but "how are we supposed to translate it into action? They need to pinpoint where and how much it is going to rain. The report had also found several loopholes in the disaster management mechanism of the country at national level, including the ineffectiveness of the National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA), headed by the prime minister. NDMA, whose mandate is to prepare disaster management plans and guidelines and ensure their implementation at state and district level had never followed up with the states on these guidelines?

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